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IMPROVEMENT OF COST MANAGEMENT SYSTEM THROUGH COMPANY MANAGEMENT REPORTING

УДОСКОНАЛЕННЯ СИСТЕМИ УПРАВЛІННЯ ВИТРАТАМИ ЧЕРЕЗ УПРАВЛІНСЬКУ ЗВІТНІСТЬ КОМПАНІЇ

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Давидюк Т.В., Дун Хай. Удосконалення системи управління витратами через управлінську звітність компанії. Науково-методична стаття.

У статті визначено, що може виступати джерелом інформації про витрати для планування та контролю витрачання ресурсів у процесі виробництва, а також запропоновано у первинних документах запровадити поле «Аналітична ознака». Обґрунтовано підходи щодо групування витрат за: економічними елементами; статтями калькуляції; місцями виникнення витрат; процесами. Визначено порядок побудови плану рахунків ведення управлінського обліку витрат, а також запропоновано відкриття субрахунків до рахунку «Виробництво» та план рахунків за аналітичними ознаками для виробничих підприємств. Встановлено, які форми управлінської звітності за ключовими показниками діяльності сприятиме оперативному управлінню витрати. Запропонований форму звіт про виробничу собівартість.

Ключові слова: витрати, менеджмент, управлінський облік, управлінська звітність, групування витрат, план рахунків управлінського обліку

Davydiuk T.V., Dong Hai. Improvement of Cost Management System through Company Management Reporting. Scientific and methodical article.

The paper defines what can be a source of cost information for planning and controlling the consumption of resources in the production process, and also proposes to introduce the field "Analytical Characteristic" in primary documents. Approaches to grouping costs by: economic elements; costing items; places of cost occurrence; processes are substantiated. The procedure for constructing a chart of accounts for management accounting of costs is determined, and the opening of subaccounts to the "Production" account and a chart of accounts by analytical features for manufacturing enterprises is proposed. The forms of management reporting on key performance indicators are identified that will facilitate operational cost management. The form of production cost report is proposed.

Keywords: costs, management, management accounting, management reporting, cost grouping, chart of accounts of management accounting

One of the current tasks of a company's CFO is to manage costs, as due that it is possible to determine not only the cost of production and how to reduce it without losing quality, but also how much the company has spent on maintaining a particular structural division. To do this, you need to group all expenses, develop a chart of accounts for management accounting and reporting forms. Unlike financial and tax accounting, which are strictly regulated by standards and legislation, management accounting is conducted in accordance with the information needs of the management of a particular company. Therefore, there are many different approaches to the organization of management accounting at an enterprise, methods of its maintenance, and even to the definition of management accounting.

The main purpose of management accounting at an enterprise is to provide management with the most complete information necessary for effective work. Management accounting is often used by an enterprise on the initiative of top management, which lacks specific management information. We agree with the opinion of H. Kurylo that "accounting will meet the needs of business (investors) only when management (internal) accounting is created on a scientific basis and only then correct accounting is organized" [1].

Developing and implementing management accounting and reporting system requires a lot of effort and time (this process can take several months at large enterprises) and does not immediately yield results. It will take time to test the system and to accumulate information that will help to adjust the management accounting system in the process of its implementation.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Many works by both domestic and foreign researchers have been devoted to the issues of the need for management reporting, the procedure for organizing and the methodology of its formation. The study of I. Yaremko and M. Zavorotnyi [2] is devoted to the disclosure of the basic principles and features of the formation of management reporting, determination of its role and place in modern management and planning systems at domestic enterprises, formulation of general directions for building management accounting and reporting on its basis to improve the efficiency of management systems. A. Yasinska [3] paid attention to the study of the methodology of building management reporting for the needs of enterprise management, highlighting the main stages of its construction and identifying the main tasks at each of them. I. Sadovska, O. Nuzhna, K. Nahirska proposed formats of management reports in the system of economic security of agricultural business enterprises [4]. K. Bezverkhyi discusses the implementation of the principle of sustainability and comparability of integrated reporting in the practical activities of domestic enterprises in his article [5]. Based on the analysis of cost management tools, L. Shevtsiv proposed a classification of costs and testing of cost management methods in terms of goals at the strategic, tactical and operational levels and centers of responsibility [6]. L. Chyzhevska (2021) in her study proposed the term "life cycle of a management report", which means a period of time that includes the development, implementation and use of a management report until the user's requests for information are satisfied [7]. A team of foreign scientists conducted a study on the growing volume of information in the activities of Slovak companies and found that management accounting contributes to the timely detection of errors, deviations and shortcomings, provides the potential to eliminate them in the form of important information [8]. Hakobyan A. and Gasparyan V. (Gasparyan, Hakobyan, 2023) proposed a methodology for management accounting of the results of social responsibility of organizations, which complements the requirements of international accounting standards IFRS-S [9].

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The trend in recent years has been an increasing understanding by company management of the need to maintain cost management accounting and prepare management reports. After all, it is such management accounting that allows to detail the accounting of information on the occurrence and distribution of costs, to generate information with varying degrees of analytical detail in the appropriate time interval that meets the needs of the company management. And the reporting generated on the basis of this management accounting can satisfy the information needs of the company managers. The content and frequency of preparation may differ for different enterprises, which may be due to the specifics and nature of the company activities, the peculiarity of its organizational and financial structure.

The aim of the article is to identify areas for improving the cost management system through analytical detailing in the appropriate time interval, which meets the needs of the company management by identifying sources of information on the company costs; areas of cost grouping; development of a chart of accounts for management accounting and management reporting forms.

The main part

In order to form an accounting system that allows obtaining reliable data on the company costs for the production of goods, maintenance of structural divisions, and various business processes, the following steps should be taken in sequence: 1) identify sources of information about the company expenses; 2) group homogeneous expenses; 3) develop a chart of accounts for management accounting; 4) develop management reporting forms.

The source of information on expenses can be both primary accounting documents and intercompany invoices, claims, payrolls, etc. In addition, for certain types of expenses (usually direct production costs), operational data on the actual consumption of basic resources may be used. For example, technological rates of raw material consumption, readings of electricity meters used for technological purposes, etc.

Information on expenses is recorded in accounting depending on the method chosen by the company. When accounting for actual resource consumption, write-offs are made based on the data of primary documents. When accounting for planned costs, technological standards for the release of materials, raw materials or other resources into production are set. The amount of resources consumed is calculated based on the price multiplied by the planned amount of resource consumption set for a particular type of product. In this case, deviations of actual costs from planned costs are reflected in accounting in both value and quantity. The information obtained in this way allows to plan and control the consumption rates of basic resources in the process of production of goods (works, services).

To identify costs, especially when accounting is performed by several analytical features, a special field "Analytical Characteristic" can be introduced in the forms of primary accounting documents, in which to indicate the type of product, the name of the division, and the type of delivery (transportation costs). This information will help simplify the analysis and management of the company costs.

The development of analytics areas for further analysis of the company's expenses should begin with the definition of the principles of cost grouping. The following groupings are most common in the activities of companies: by economic elements (types) of costs; by costing items; by places of cost occurrence; by processes. In the process of implementing a management accounting system, it is recommended to use the provisions of the

US Institute of Management Accounting (Statements on Management Accounting, SMA) when accounting for expenses. Currently, more than 60 SMAs have been developed.

The provisions governing the accounting of expenses include the following:

- Allocation of Service and Administrative Costs (SMA 4B);
- Definition and Measurement of Direct Labor Cost (SMA 4C);
- Definition and Measurement of Direct Material Cost (SMA 4E);
- Allocation of Information Systems Costs (SMA 4F);
- Accounting for Indirect Production Costs (SMA 4G);
- Cost Management for Freight Transportation (SMA 4I);
- application of process-oriented cost management (Implementing Activity Based Costing, SMA 4T);
- using the Implementing Target Costing (SMA 4FF) system.

Cost grouping by economic elements is necessary to determine what resources have been spent and what is the share of certain types of expenses in their total amount. In general, material costs (raw materials, electricity, fuel, etc.), labor costs of production workers, social contributions from their salaries, services of third-party companies, taxes, depreciation, and other costs can be grouped into the following categories.

Costs grouped by economic elements are always primary and do not contain derivative costs. For example, labor and material costs incurred by an enterprise to repair buildings and structures on its own will be reflected in management accounting by type not as "Expenses for repair of buildings and structures" but as "Labor costs" and "Raw materials". Or, for example, advertising produced by the company itself using the services of third-party companies are accounted for under the items "Salaries and wages", "Raw materials" and "Services of third-party companies", rather than "Advertising expenses".

Cost grouping by costing items allows to analyze the purposes for which resources were spent. The list of items is determined by each company based on the need for detailed information. The following list of costing items is quite common: direct raw materials and supplies; returnable waste; purchased semi-finished products and components; fuel and energy for technological purposes; semi-finished products of own production; basic wages of employees; additional wages of employees; social contributions from employees' wages; production development costs; general production costs; other production costs.

To analyze the efficiency of a particular structural division, cost grouping by places of its occurrence is used. In this grouping, expenses are attributed to the costs of those divisions of the company where the resources were used. As a rule, cost grouping by place of cost occurrence is performed in accordance with the financial structure of the company. In a manufacturing company, the cost centers may include the main and auxiliary production divisions, commercial and administrative services. In trading companies, accounting is often performed within the commercial, auxiliary and general business divisions.

The choice of cost grouping type is determined by the specifics of the business. The basis for cost grouping can be both product type and financial responsibility centers. Mixed groupings can also be applied – by shop principle and by product type simultaneously. For companies engaged in the production of agricultural products, grouping by the place of cost occurrence may be applied – in fact, "by fields", for processing enterprises of the group – by centers of responsibility (workshops), for sales divisions – by type of product. By tracking how the costs of finished products are formed by responsibility center, the CFO can gain a certain leverage over the line structural divisions, pointing out certain shortcomings in their work, for example, exceeding the cost limit set in the budget. If costs are constantly rising, it is important to understand their causes and strictly control them.

In the practice of Western companies, there are no regulatory requirements for determining costing items, so they are based on economic feasibility. Here are the costing items of an Austrian company: direct material costs; direct production costs; general production costs; production development costs; costs associated with equipment and production downtime; other production costs; warehouse and transportation logistics costs; promotion and advertising costs; R&D costs; sales organization costs; administrative costs.

Cost grouping by process involves generalizing costs depending on the direction of their use – in production, sales or management of the company. This makes it possible to estimate the cost of the company's processes, which, in turn, makes it possible to more accurately determine the final cost of the goods (works, services) produced.

As a rule, business processes are divided into main and auxiliary processes. The main ones include procurement, storage and transportation, production, and sales. The auxiliary processes include marketing, R&D, quality assurance, human resources and information management.

The universal system for accounting for company costs in terms of types of resources, areas of their use, and places where expenses are incurred can be represented as a cube.

To develop analytics for cost accounting, we suggest using one of two approaches. A more complex, but also more complete system is the one where all three dimensions of the cost cube (types, uses, and places of cost occurrence) are used in the chart of accounts. In this case, accounting is maintained on subaccounts or by analytical characteristics (subaccounts) of expense accounts in at least three analytical sections. But most often, the two dimensions of the cube are combined into one, for example, grouping by type and use of expenses. For example, when an expense item contains not only an indication of the resource used, but also the direction of expenditure: fuels and lubricants for passenger vehicles, fuels and lubricants for freight vehicles, fuels and

lubricants for production needs. Such a system is simpler, but it may not always provide the required level of detail of cost information.

The chart of accounts for management accounting is built taking into account the approach to cost grouping described above. We offer two approaches to its formation:

1. Cost grouping is subaccounts of the respective synthetic accounts (Table 1).

Table 1. Suggested subaccounts of a manufacturing enterprise opened to the "Production" account (excerpt)

Account number	Name of the object of accounting
...	...
23.204	Production of stamps for hot and cold metal processing
23.2040000	Production of stamps for hot and cold metal processing
23.2040100	Materials.
23.2040200	Purchased semi-finished products
23.2040300	Waste
23.2040400	Fuel and energy for technological processes
23.2040500	Basic salary of employees
23.2040700	Contributions to social activities
23.2041000	Cost of special tools
23.2041100	Maintenance and operation of equipment
23.2041200	General production costs
23.2041400	Losses from defects
23.205	Tool manufacturing
...	...

Source: authors' own elaboration

2. Cost grouping is an analytical characteristic (subaccounts) of synthetic accounts or subaccounts (Table 2).

Table 2. Proposed chart of accounts of a manufacturing enterprise (based on the example of the Ukrainian chart of accounts) (excerpt)

Code	Name	Subaccount 1	Subaccount 2	Subaccount 3
...				
23	Production	Subdivisions	Cost items	
23.01	Main production	Subdivisions	Cost items	
23.07	Production of goods from tolling raw materials	Nomenclature, design	Commodity values	Storage locations
25	Semi-finished products	Nomenclature, design	Commodity values	Storage locations
23.02	Auxiliary production	Subdivisions	Cost items	
24	Defects in production			
28.01	Deficiency in respect of tax-exempt activities	Nomenclature, design	Commodity values	Storage locations
28.02	Deficiency in respect of nontax-exempt activities	Nomenclature, design	Commodity values	Storage locations
23.03	Servicing industries and households	Subdivisions	Cost items	
26	Finished products	Nomenclature, design	Commodity values	Storage locations
91	General production costs	Subdivisions	Cost items	
93	Selling expenses	Subdivisions	Cost items	
...				

Source: authors' own elaboration

In the management accounting of Ukrainian enterprises, production costs are recorded in accounts 23 "Production" and 91 "General production costs". In separate structural subdivisions, accounting can be kept on subaccounts and by analytical characteristics (types of products, divisions). The parent company can receive the necessary information on a daily basis in the form of a current income statement, where expenses can be summarized – production costs, administrative costs, and sales costs.

The account number may have the following structure: 23 XXX YYY 0. The first two characters are the account number according to the chart of accounts (like in Ukraine) (23.02 – Auxiliary production), the next three characters – XXX – are assigned based on the classifier "Type of products (works, services) for auxiliary production" (stamps for cold and hot metal processing), then three characters – YYY – from the classifier "Cost item for auxiliary production" (materials, fuel and energy, etc.), the last character – 0 – is free character.

The last step is to develop management reporting forms. The main difference between management reporting and financial reporting is the degree of detail, the way it is grouped, and the degree of accuracy of the information: this reporting is more operational, and its data may be based on assumptions made by the company managers. In addition, management reporting is an internal affair of each company, so the procedure for its

submission is regulated by internal documents, and the forms are developed by managers. For example, at the level of the workshop – cost center – a report on the execution of the cost estimate, containing a list of controlled costs, planned and actual data, and deviations, can be used, at the level of the enterprise – profit center – a profit report can be used. Since the profit center is responsible for both costs and profits, such a report can include expenses and revenues of the company divisions.

As management reports on costs, reports on budget execution by the cost center, as well as a summary report on the cost of production (Table 3), planned and actual costing for orders, processes, and redistributions can be used, depending on how management cost accounting is organized. Management income statements, which usually contain aggregated data, may additionally include cost breakdowns by type of product (work, service).

Table 3. Proposed report on production cost

Workshop _____			
Products			
No. s/n	Name of the cost item	Total expenses	Share in the total amount
1	Raw materials for technological purposes		
1.1	Raw materials and inputs		
1.2	Chemical reagents (except catalysts and sorbents)		
2	Auxiliary materials		
2.1	Sorbents and catalysts		
2.2	...		
2.4	Other materials		
3	Semi-finished products of own production		
4	Returnable waste (deductible)		
5	Purchased semi-finished products, components, ... works and services of a production nature performed by contractors		
5.1	...		
6	All types of fuel for technological purposes		
6.1	Natural gas		
6.2	Hydrogen		
7	Energy of all kinds for technological purposes		
7.1	Electricity		
7.2	Steam		
7.3	Cold		
7.4	Compressed air		
7.5	Technical water		
8	Remuneration of production workers directly involved in the production of goods		
8.1	Basic salary		
8.2	Additional salary		
9	Contributions to social activities		
10	Transportation and procurement costs		
11	Expenses for preparation and development of production		
12	Depreciation of production assets and provision for capital repairs		
12.1	Depreciation of property, plant and equipment		
12.2	Provision for major repairs		
13	General production costs		
14	Other production costs		
15	By-products (deductible)		
16	Production cost		
	Total		

Source: authors' own elaboration

The composition, content, and forms of management reporting should be developed with due regard to the following principles:

- relevance (management reporting should be useful for making specific management decisions, not just informing about certain aspects of the company's activities);
- efficiency;
- targeting (reporting should be provided to specific managers according to their place in the management hierarchy);
- sufficiency (information in the reporting should be sufficient to make management decisions at the appropriate level, while it should not be excessive and distract managers' attention to insignificant or irrelevant information);
- analytical (management reporting should provide for the possibility of further analysis with minimal time);
- clarity;

- reliability;
- compatibility (comparability of management reporting enables users to identify similarities and differences between data presented in several reporting packages. Comparability is achieved by using the same accounting principles in similar transactions and conditions).

All management reporting can be grouped into the following three blocks:

- management reporting on the financial position, performance and changes in the financial position of the enterprise;
- management reporting on key performance indicators;
- management reporting on the implementation of the company budgets.

The main differences between management accounts and financial statements are the degree of detail (management accounts provide more detailed analytical information), the way information is grouped (in management accounts, data may be grouped according to principles different from financial ones) and the degree of accuracy of the information (in some cases, especially in operational management reports, certain errors and the use of approximate data are allowed).

When developing a methodology for preparing and processing management reports, a balanced approach is required to determine the timing of such reports, the amount of data, and their format. For example, monthly management reports are prepared between the 5th and 10th day of the month following the reporting month. However, a situation may arise when the company owner or CEO needs at least approximate reporting for the current month as early as the 29th day of the month, i.e., before the end of the reporting period. In this case, you can use business simulation models, which can be used to generate long-term forecasts and monthly budgets. The model enters the currently available data and extrapolates it to the days remaining until the end of the reporting period. The result is management reporting based mainly on actual data, but with certain assumptions. As a rule, the accuracy of such a calculation is quite sufficient for making operational management decisions by the company management.

Each company develops management reporting based primarily on its needs for management information. On the one hand, without all the information, the company management will not be able to make informed decisions, and on the other hand, if there is too much information, it becomes more difficult for the manager to identify the most important data that has the greatest impact on the company's development.

The management accounts of an industrial holding company may be presented as follows:

1. Standard management reports on the financial position, performance and changes in the financial position of the company:

- 1.1. Management balance sheet.
- 1.2. Management income statement.
- 1.3. Management report on cash flows:

1.3.1. Management Statement of Cash Flows 1 (direct method – a method of calculating net cash inflows/outflows from operating activities. It is calculated as the difference between income secured by real cash inflows and expenses related to real payments).

1.3.2. Management Statement of Cash Flows 2 (indirect method – a method of calculating cash flows from operating activities in which net profit or loss is adjusted to take into account the results of non-cash transactions, any deferrals or accruals of previous periods or future operating cash inflows or payments and income or expense items related to investment or financing cash flows).

2. Management reporting on key performance indicators.
3. Management reporting on budget execution (Table 4).

Table 4. Management reporting by key performance indicators (KPIs)

KPI groups	Examples of KPIs
1	2
<i>KPIs characterizing the efficiency of the business as a whole (management level – president, CEO)</i>	
Shareholder satisfaction indicators	Return on assets; return on cash flow; company value
Customer satisfaction indicators	Total number of customer complaints; customer turnover; number of regular customers
Employee satisfaction and performance indicators	labor productivity; staff turnover
<i>KPIs characterizing the efficiency of business processes and individual functional areas (management level – vice presidents, deputy general directors, heads of services and departments)</i>	
Procurement performance indicators	Supply quality index; goods transit time
Efficiency indicators of storage and movement of goods	Speed of commodity turnover; cost of storage losses; cost of transportation losses
Production efficiency indicators	Production volume; production nomenclature
Sales performance indicators	Share of discounts in sales; customer base coverage; sales profitability
Performance indicators of after-sales service	Costs of defect correction; quality index of claims resolution
R&D performance indicators	Average life cycle of new products; number of new products under development

Continuation of Table 4

1	2
Quality indicators	Certification costs; reject rate
Personnel performance indicators	Ratio of payroll to sales; staff turnover; number of employees hired versus number of applicants
Financial indicators	Liquidity ratios; profitability ratios; turnover ratios; operating leverage
Performance indicators of information technology use	Return on IT investments; satisfaction of key business divisions with the level of IT support
<i>KPIs characterizing the efficiency of individual divisions (management level – vice presidents, deputy general directors, heads of services and departments)</i>	
The same indicators are used to evaluate the performance of departments as are used to evaluate business processes or functional areas that are the responsibility of specific departments	labor productivity (for the production department); staff turnover (for the sales department and other departments)

Source: authors' own elaboration

After the company has built a cost management system and generated reports, it is possible to analyze the growth rate of costs, calculate the cost of production, and develop cost reduction measures.

Conclusions

The identified areas for improving the cost management system meet the needs of the company management. They are based on the identification of such sources of information on the company costs that will allow planning and controlling the consumption rates of basic resources in the process of production of goods (works, services). The development of analytical areas for further analysis of the company costs should begin with the definition of the principles of cost grouping, among which may be grouping by economic elements necessary to determine what resources are spent and what is the share of certain types of expenses in their total amount. Cost grouping by costing items allows to analyze the purposes for which resources were spent, and cost grouping by place of occurrence will help analyze the efficiency of the company structural divisions. Companies can also group costs by process, depending on the direction of resource use – in production, sales, or management. In addition, it is important to build a chart of accounts and management reporting forms that will allow to group information about the company costs with varying degrees of detail.

Abstract

One of the current tasks of a company's CFO is to manage costs, as due that it is possible to determine not only the cost of production and how to reduce it without losing quality, but also how much the company has spent on maintaining a particular structural division. To do this, you need to group all expenses, develop a chart of accounts for management accounting and reporting forms.

Unlike financial and tax accounting, which are strictly regulated by standards and legislation, management accounting is conducted in accordance with the information needs of the management of a particular company. Therefore, there are many different approaches to the organization of management accounting at an enterprise, methods of its maintenance, and even to the definition of management accounting.

The main purpose of management accounting at an enterprise is to provide management with the most complete information necessary for effective work. Management accounting is often used by an enterprise on the initiative of top management, which lacks specific management information.

Developing and implementing management accounting and reporting system requires a lot of effort and time (this process can take several months at large enterprises) and does not immediately yield results. It will take time to test the system and to accumulate information that will help to adjust the management accounting system in the process of its implementation.

The purpose of the article is to identify areas for improving the cost management system through analytical detailing in the appropriate time interval, which meets the needs of the company management by identifying sources of information on the company costs; areas of cost grouping; development of a chart of accounts for management accounting and management reporting forms.

The identified areas for improving the cost management system meet the needs of the company management. They are based on the identification of such sources of information about the company costs that will allow planning and controlling the consumption rates of basic resources in the process of production of goods (works, services). The development of analytical areas for further analysis of the company costs should begin with the definition of the principles of cost grouping, among which may be grouping by economic elements necessary to determine what resources are spent and what is the share of certain types of expenses in their total amount. Cost grouping by costing items allows to analyze the purposes for which resources were spent, and cost grouping by place of occurrence will help analyze the efficiency of the company structural divisions. Companies can also group costs by process, depending on the direction of resource use – in production, sales, or management. In addition, it is important to build a chart of accounts and management reporting forms that will allow to group information about the company costs with varying degrees of detail.

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